

CONSTITUTIONAL AND LEGAL WAYS TO PROTECT INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the grounds and procedure for considering disputes related to the protection of intellectual property. Based on the analysis of the norms of legislation, the regulation of the constitutional and legal ways of protecting the complex of rights included in the category of intellectual property is determined.

I. Introduction

The current stage of development of society is characterized by the isolation of derivative objects of legal regulation, the large-scale impact of various kinds of technologies on all spheres of human life, as well as the complication of the functional mechanism of interaction between substantive and procedural law. These factors indirectly, and in most cases directly affect the totality of categories of civil law, in particular intellectual property. Therefore, it is important to systematically improve the regulatory framework, timely eliminate emerging gaps in legislation, and, in addition to all of the above, ensure the full range of protection of property rights and intangible benefits in the field of intellectual property. But, in this case, a number of questions arise regarding the regulation of constitutional and legal methods for protecting a set of rights included in the category of intellectual property.

II. Materials and methods

Therefore, for an extensive and comprehensive analysis of the above task, it is necessary to fully characterize the term "intellectual property" itself. In this case, the normative definition is reduced to the consideration of legislative acts that reveal the meaning of the specified term. But in order to move on to a full-fledged concept of intellectual property, it is important to determine that "The right of ownership is the right of a person to own, use and dispose of his property at his own discretion and in his own interests, and also to demand the elimination of any violations of his property right, from whom whatever they come from" (Article 164 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan) [1]. The application of this rule to the category of intellectual property is regulated by the provision that land, subsoil, water, air space, flora and fauna and other natural resources, enterprises, things, including buildings, apartments,

structures, equipment can be owned, raw materials and products, money, securities and other property, as well as objects of intellectual property (Article 169 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan). Based on this, we can conclude that the right to intellectual property is an inalienable right of every citizen, which is established and protected not only by the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, but also by the Constitution, which states: "Everyone has the right to property" (Article 36 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan). Uzbekistan) [2].

It is important to note that the legal and regulatory analysis of the current acts of national legislation allows us to establish that there is no exhaustive categorization of the term intellectual property. The above statement also applies to the theoretical characterization of the concept of "intellectual property", as various scientific theories are put forward that reveal part of the content of intangible goods. In any case, it is not appropriate to consider intellectual property as a category consisting only of personal or only property rights. After all, its essence consists in the totality of these relations, and not their isolation.

Therefore, the concept of "intellectual property" is constantly being improved by making certain additions. This is explained by the fact that the content of all intellectual property relations is difficult to characterize with one definition. The legislation (Article 1031 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan) [1] provides for the following classification of intellectual property objects:

1) results of intellectual activity: works of science, literature and art; performances, phonograms, programs of on-air or cable broadcasting organizations; programs for

electronic computers and databases; inventions, utility models, industrial designs; selection achievements; undisclosed information, including production secrets (know-how);

2) means of individualization of participants in civil circulation, goods, works and services: company names; trademarks (service marks); appellations of origin of goods;

3) other results of intellectual activity and means of individualization of participants in civil circulation, goods, works and services in cases provided for by this Code or other laws.

In this context, it should be defined that the category of intellectual property includes copyright and related rights. Copyright extends to works of science, literature and art, which are the result of creative activity, regardless of the purpose and dignity of the work, as well as the way it is expressed. And in turn, the objects of related rights include performances, phonograms, broadcasts of on-air or cable broadcasting organizations (Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Copyright and Related Rights" dated July 20, 2006 No. ZRU-42) [3].

The theoretical basis of the study was the scientific works of such authors as Okyulov O.[4,5], Karakhodzhaeva D.M. [6], Burkhanova L.M. [7,8,9,10,11,12] and others who considered some theoretical and practical issues of legal protection of intellectual property in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The study used methods of analysis of the current civil legislation, generalization of legal material with the formulation of conclusions, as well as system analysis, a comparison method.

III. Analysis of the results of the study

The whole range of objects included in the concept of "Intellectual Property" plays an important role in the activities of all members of society, affecting various aspects of his life. The active use and influence of the Internet and the scientific development of technical processes dramatically affect the change in the content of the institution of intellectual property. Therefore, the issue of providing legal protection and protecting the possibility of a person to establish authorship on the results of creative and other activities within the framework of the legal regulation of the provisions on intellectual property becomes relevant.

The protection of intellectual property can be characterized as a set of measures aimed at recognizing or restoring the rights and protecting the interests of their owners in case of their violation or contestation.

Consequently, the right to judicial protection is a constitutional right and is enshrined in Article 3 of the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan[13], which states that "In accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, everyone is guaranteed judicial protection of his rights, freedoms and legitimate interests. Any interested person has the right, in accordance with the procedure established by the legislation on civil proceedings, to apply to a civil court (court) for the protection of a violated or disputed right, or an interest protected by law. In this context, it should be noted that practical experience points to the resolution of disputes relating to intellectual property in civil courts. Since, it is these courts that have jurisdiction over this category of cases. Moreover, it is possible to consider cases related to the violation of intellectual

property rights, both in the court of first instance, and in the courts of appeal and cassation instances.

But then the question arises: how does the Constitutional Court participate in the protection of property rights and intangible benefits in the field of intellectual property?

To answer this question, it is necessary, in accordance with the Constitutional Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [14], to characterize the Constitutional Court as part of the judicial system of the Republic of Uzbekistan: "The Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a permanent judicial authority that considers cases on constitutionality legislative and executive acts.

It should be noted that the Constitutional Court exercises its powers in a different way than the Supreme or other courts of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan, on the basis of the norms of the Constitutional Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the Rules of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan[15].

Thus, the identification of opportunities for the protection of intellectual property by the Constitutional Court is carried out by categorizing the powers of the Constitutional Court on the basis of the norms of Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan".

IV. Findings

The main points that exist both in the Republic of Uzbekistan and in many other

countries related to the protection of intellectual property are as follows.

First. In accordance with part 3 of article 29 “Requirements for applying to the Constitutional Court” of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan” [14], complaints from citizens and legal entities must indicate the fact that the case is being considered in court and the use of all forms of judicial protection . Thus, citizens and legal entities, applying to the Constitutional Court with a complaint about checking the constitutionality of a law, if the law, in their opinion, violates their constitutional rights and freedoms, does not comply with the Constitution and is applied in a specific case, consideration of which in a court of general jurisdiction of any instance completed and thus all other remedies have been exhausted. It should be noted that the inclusion of such a mechanism for the protection of violated rights serves as the implementation of Article 44 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, where everyone is guaranteed judicial protection of their rights and freedoms.

Moreover, as defined in Article 73 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan” [14], the legal force of the decision of the Constitutional Court is final and not subject to appeal. A normative legal act or part thereof, recognized as inconsistent with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan by decision of the Constitutional Court, ceases to be valid.

That is, the Constitutional Court is the last instance in the procedural chain of consideration of a case in the entire judicial system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Second. The Constitutional Court determines the compliance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan of the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan and resolutions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees, resolutions and orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, government resolutions, decisions of local government bodies, interstate contractual and other obligations of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This means that by recognizing that a certain normative legal act does not comply with the Constitution, in the field of intellectual property, the violated property right and intangible benefits are protected. If this act renders unlawful, from the point of view of consistency with the Constitution, regulation, then the Constitutional Court decides on its inconsistency, thereby limiting or terminating its impact on legal relations.

Third. The Constitutional Court, on the basis of the norms of Article 28 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan” [14], considers the appeal of state bodies and officials who have the right to appeal to the Constitutional Court, as well as complaints from citizens and legal entities whose constitutional rights and freedoms, in their opinion, violated by the law applied in a particular case, which is not consistent with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Fourth. The Constitutional Court gives interpretation of the norms of the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In practice, sometimes there are cases of ambiguity of a specific legal norm, which complicates the functioning of the legal mechanism. In this case, the constitutional court explains the meaning

and content of the rule of law, revealing a specific legal uncertainty. The specified interpretation will be generally binding in subsequent law enforcement. Consequently, constitutional and legal coordination of disputes relating to the category of intellectual property is also possible here.

To carry out its main function - the interpretation of the norms of the Constitution and the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Constitutional Court, in accordance with part 1 of Article 30 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [14] has the right to demand from the person who applies to the court, an annex to the appeal and the text of a normative legal act to be verified, or the norms of the Constitution and the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan to be interpreted. This is explained by the fact that one of the main subjects of the dispute under consideration in the Constitutional Court is precisely the interpretation of the norms of the Constitution, and its compliance with the provisions of the norms of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan under consideration, subject to interpretation.

Moreover, paragraph 1 of part 2 of article 29 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [14] provides that the appeal submitted to the Constitutional Court must indicate the name, number, date of adoption, source of publication of the regulatory legal act, the constitutionality of which is subject to verification, the provisions of the Constitution and the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, subject to interpretation.

Part 3 of Article 53 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [14] determines that the Constitutional Court may consider cases to determine the compliance of decisions of local government bodies with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, official interpretation of the norms of laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan without oral hearings. But the Constitutional Court must issue a ruling on this and notify the participants in the constitutional proceedings.

An important point is that the content of the decision of the Constitutional Court in the introductory part indicates the norms of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan", in accordance with which the Constitutional Court considered this case. And in the reasoning part of the decision, the actual circumstances of the case, established by the Constitutional Court and underlying the decision, are indicated; evidence on which the court's conclusions about the circumstances of the case are based; regulatory legal acts that guided the Constitutional Court when making a decision.

All these provisions are aimed at the correct and comprehensive consideration by the Constitutional Court of cases related to the interpretation of specific norms of legislation, and their compliance with the provisions of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Fifth. But in this context, it is important to note that the Constitutional Court, in the exercise of its powers, refrains from establishing and investigating factual

circumstances in all cases when it falls within the competence of other courts or other bodies.

In accordance with Article 82 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [14], the Constitutional Court decides on specific legal acts, the constitutionality of which is questioned. The Constitutional Court has the right, having checked the constitutionality of a normative legal act, at the same time to make a decision also in relation to normative legal acts based on the verified act or reproducing its provisions, although they were not mentioned in the appeal submitted to the Constitutional Court for consideration. Based on the results of consideration of cases on checking the constitutionality of laws, the Constitutional Court has the right, having recognized the law or part of it as consistent with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to give an official interpretation of the norms of this law if ambiguities are found in them that led to incorrect or contradictory practice of applying this law or part of it.

Consideration of cases in the Constitutional Court takes place on the basis of the Rules of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Rules of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Article 10) [15] determine that a normative legal act is considered constitutional until its inconsistency with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is established by a decision of the Constitutional Court adopted as a result of the trial.

The Rules (Article 11) [15] provide for a comprehensive, complete and objective verification of the circumstances of the

case when considering issues, since the Constitutional Court is not bound by the arguments of the parties, not limited to the materials presented, explanations and testimonies, is obliged to take all measures for a comprehensive, complete and objective verification of the circumstances of the case, ensuring the rights of the parties, other participants, the proper performance by them of their duties.

An important component enshrined in the Regulations (Article 56) [15] is the conduct of an examination and the possibility of hearing the conclusions and opinions of experts and specialists. The Constitutional Court may appoint an expert examination, the production of which is entrusted to scientific institutions or specific specialists who have the necessary knowledge and sufficient experience in the relevant specialty. Issues on which an expert should give an opinion are determined by the reporting judge or the Constitutional Court. Such a situation in cases involving violation of the provisions of intellectual property law can be decisive.

The Rules (Article 74) [15] determine which cases are subject to consideration in the Constitutional Court - this is the proceedings on the interpretation of the norms of the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The official interpretation of the norms of the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan is carried out in case of detection of ambiguities in them, incorrect or contradictory practice of their application. In the decision or appeal to introduce the issue of official interpretation of the norms of the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, arguments and evidence of ambiguities, incorrect or

contradictory practice of their application must be indicated.

The protection of intellectual property rights by the Constitutional Court is not only the responsibility of the state, but also a guarantee of ensuring the rights and freedoms of both individuals and legal entities in the field of exercising the entire complex of intellectual property rights, entrepreneurship, and access to information.

There are certain ways of constitutional and legal protection of intellectual property, the most important of which can be called the recognition of the provisions of the law as inconsistent with the norms of the Constitution; interpretation of the norms of the Constitution; identification of

legal uncertainty in the legal regulation of certain issues in the field of intellectual property; publication on the official website of the Constitutional Court of a court decision on the violation committed, indicating the conditions for eliminating such violations in the implementation of intellectual property rights.

In conclusion, based on all the above facts, we can conclude that the participation of the Constitutional Court in the legal protection of persons whose rights, freedoms and legitimate interests have been violated is multifunctional. Since, through the exercise of its powers, this body eliminates a number of obstacles to the implementation, including intellectual property rights.

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